

π -Electron currents in fully aromatic benzenoids[†]

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Abs.ract : In view of different patterns of π -electron density currents reported by *ab initio* calculations for cata- and peri-condensed compounds, we consider π -electron currents of fully benzenoid cata-condensed tetrabenzoanthracene and peri-condensed dibenzopyrene in order to discern the pattern of ring currents in fully benzenoid hydrocarbons, rings of which have either π -sextets or are "empty" in the terminology of Clar. Our graph theoretical calculations of π -electron currents is based on calculations of contributions from conjugated circuits of individual Kekulé valence structures of these molecules.

Keywords : Graph theoretical calculation, π -electron currents, benzenoid cata-condensed tetrabenzoanthracene, peri-condensed dibenzopyrene.

Introduction

The calculations of π -electron currents in polycyclic conjugated hydrocarbon when placed in homogenous magnetic field have received attention already in the early days of Quantum Chemistry¹⁻³. These early approaches used the HMO (Hückel Molecular Orbital) model and focused on calculating currents in individual rings of polycyclic compounds. Interest in ring current calculations continued as is reflected by numerous publication, selection of which include Refs. 4-8. The same problem was considered more recently using *ab initio* computations, but with a difference that no any prior assumptions about currents were made, and results merely reported the calculated density of currents over the molecules⁹⁻¹⁴. For a number of peri-condensed conjugated compounds (e.g. isomers of coronene) the results of such *ab initio* calculations revealed that the dominant current is along the molecular periphery with minor currents in their interior¹⁵. However, in the case of a number of cata-condensed benzenoid hydrocarbons, in contrast the same *ab initio* calculations show that the dominant π -electron currents were confined to the interior part of molecules periphery. Similar qualitative results have been also reported on HMO

calculations of ring currents in anthracene and tetracene¹⁶.

Recently Randić *et al.*, have outlined a novel graph theoretical approach to calculation of π -electron currents in planar polycyclic conjugated hydrocarbons^{17,18}. In this approach one considers contributions from conjugated circuits within the set of molecular Kekulé valence structures. Clearly this approach is unrelated to MO methodology, whether based on HMO calculations or based on highly elaborate *ab initio* methods using Gaussian RHF6-31G** orbitals¹⁹. A very satisfactory parallelism was found between the graph theoretical results and the *ab initio* computations for both cata-condensed and peri-condensed polycyclic conjugated hydrocarbons. Because of the different patterns of π -electron currents in cata- and peri-condensed compounds it is of interest to investigate what kind of π -electron currents will emerge for fully benzenoid hydrocarbons, which can be both, cata- and peri-condensed, what is the goal of this research. We selected for examination the following four fully benzenoid hydrocarbons : a pair of cata-condensed benzenoids, triphenylene and tetrabenzoanthracene, and a pair of peri-condensed hydrocarbons : dibenzopyrene and tribenzoperilene (Fig. 1).

[†]In honour of Professor Padmakar V. Khadikar.

Fig. 1. Fully benzenoid cata-condensed triphenylene and tetrabenzanthracene and peri-condensed dibenzopyrene and tribenzopyrene considered in this article.

Outline of the approach

The graph theoretical approach was introduced and been outlined recently in Ref. 20. Briefly, it is based on *conjugated circuits*, which are circuits within individual Kekulé valence structures in which there is regular alternation of CC single and double bonds²⁰⁻²⁴. In Fig. 2 we have illustrated ten out of 20 Kekulé valence structures of

dibenzopyrene, the remaining ten structures can be obtained as mirror images of the structure shown. In Fig. 3 are illustrated all conjugated circuits for the first Kekulé valence structure of Fig. 2. As one can see there are 19 different conjugated circuits in this and in all other Kekulé valence structure of dibenzopyrene, in agreement with the theorem of Gutman that a molecule having K Kekulé valence structures has $K-1$ conjugated circuits²⁵.

Fig. 2. Ten symmetry non-equivalent Kekulé valence structures of dibenzopyrene. The remaining ten Kekulé valence structures of dibenzopyrene are the mirror images of structures shown.

Fig. 3. The conjugated circuits of the first Kekulé valence structure of Fig. 2.

In the next step of the calculations one replaces CC bonds participating in a conjugated circuit by bond vectors, which symbolize the π -electron current. The direction of the π -electron current is positive (that is anti-clockwise) for conjugated circuits having $4n+2\pi$ -electrons, and negative (clockwise) for circuits having $4n$ π -electrons. After adding current contributions from all conjugated circuits in one Kekulé valence structure one obtains contribution of that valence structure to the molecular π -electron current. $4n$ conjugated circuits do not occur in benzenoid hydrocarbons but do occur in nonbenzenoid hydrocarbon, both, alternants like biphenylene (two benzene rings fused to opposite sides of a four member ring),

and non-alternants like cyclopenta[*fg*]acenaphthylene (naphthalene fragment with fused pentagons at the top and the bottom central bonds). While all non benzenoid alternant compounds having $4n$ rings necessarily have $4n$ conjugated circuits, there are non benzenoid non-alternants (polycyclic conjugated hydrocarbons having at least one odd ring) that could have only $4n+2$ conjugated circuits, like acenaphthylene $C_{16}H_{10}$ or cyclohepta[*fg*]acenaphthylene and cyclohepta[*a*]phenalene $C_{20}H_{12}$.

After finding contributions from all conjugated circuits in single Kekulé valence structure one obtains contributions of that Kekulé valence structure to molecular π -electron current. In Fig. 4 are illustrated CC bond cur-

Fig. 4. Conjugated circuits currents for the first Kekulé valence structure of dibenzopyrene.

rents for all conjugated circuits of the first Kekulé valence structure of dibenzopyrene. In Fig. 5 at top left is illustrated π -electron current pattern of the first Kekulé valence structure of dibenzopyrene of Fig. 2, based on the ten conjugated circuits of Fig. 3. The rest of Fig. 5 illustrates the π -electron current patterns for the remaining nine symmetry non-equivalent Kekulé valence structure of dibenzopyrene. When CC bond currents from all ten symmetry non-equivalent Kekulé valence structure of dibenzopyrene are combined together they result in π -electron current pattern shown at the top left of Fig. 6. A similar, symmetry related, pattern is obtained from the remaining ten mirror image Kekulé valence structure,

which is shown at the top right of Fig. 6. Finally when contributions from all 20 Kekulé valence structure of dibenzopyrene are combined together they result in π -electron current pattern shown at the bottom of Fig. 6, obtained from all 380 conjugated circuits of 20 Kekulé valence structures of dibenzopyrene.

We will later discuss the computed bond currents in dibenzopyrene, but already it is visible from Fig. 6 that four peripheral benzene rings, which are Clar's π -sextet rings of dibenzopyrene, carry the dominant bond currents. Before continuing let us state that calculations as outlined, are straightforward and not tedious at all, but for molecules having large number of Kekulé valence

Fig. 5. Patterns of π -electron induced currents for ten Kekulé valence structures of dibenzopyrene of Fig. 2.

Fig. 6. Top right : π -electron currents for the ten Kekulé valence structures of Fig. 2; Top left : π -electron currents for the mirror image ten Kekulé valence structures of Fig. 2; Bottom : The overall patterns of π -electron currents for all 20 Kekulé valence structures.

structures may soon become unpractical. For example, in the case of the last molecule of Fig. 1, tribenzoperylene, the number of Kekulé valence structures $K = 45$, leading thus to totality of 1980 conjugated circuits. The calculations of π -electron current contributions from individual Kekulé valence structures would be time consuming and error-prone, and suggest delegating such labor for larger molecules to computer, in view that algorithm for calculations of molecular π -electron current patterns is straightforward²⁶. The search for $K-1$ conjugated circuits, when K is already modest, as has been the case with molecules of Fig. 1, tetrabenzoanthracene, and dibenzoperylene, may not be so easy if carried out by inspection of individual Kekulé valence structures, but they can all be found and constructed by considering all $K-1$ pairwise superposition of K Kekulé valence structures.

Results

In Fig. 7 we show the results, the patterns of π -elec-

tron currents for cata-condensed fully benzenoid triphenylene and tetrabenzoanthracene, while in Fig. 8 are shown π -electron currents for CC bonds in peri-condensed tribenzoperylene. It is not difficult to construct conjugated circuits for so small molecule. In Fig. 9 we show all nine Kekulé valence of triphenylene, labelled as *A-I*, and in Fig. 10 we show all eight conjugated circuits of the first Kekulé valence structures. Seven out of eight conjugated circuits in eight Kekulé valence structures (*B-H*) are the same circuits as in valence structure *A*. The Kekulé valence structures *A-H* differ only in a single conjugated circuit, the last conjugated circuit of Fig. 10. In Fig. 11 we have depicted for structures *A-H* this last unique conjugated circuit. The last Kekulé valence of triphenylene, the structure *I*, however has seven unique conjugated circuits and only one conjugated circuit common (the last), which is the same as the last conjugated circuit in the structure *A*. In the lower part of Fig. 11 we have illustrated all conjugated circuit in the last Kekulé valence structure *I*.

Fig. 7. CC π -bond currents for two cata-condensed fully benzenoid hydrocarbons investigated.

By having information on all conjugated circuits it is not difficult to obtain the bond currents in individual rings of triphenylene, which follow by enumeration of bond vectors for the same bond in all conjugated circuits. Thus the terminal benzene ring appears four times in five Kekulé valence structures and five times in four Kekulé it from which it follows that π -electron in its peripheral CC bonds adds to 40. In contrast in the case of triphenylene only a single conjugated circuits contributes to the central benzene rings in eight Kekulé valence structures and in one structure there are eight conjugated circuits, adding to 16. As the result we obtain the π -electron current pattern shown in Fig. 9.

Described procedure, which takes advantage of reducing the construction of conjugated circuits in numerous Kekulé valence structures is not important for small molecules, molecules having dozen or two dozen Kekulé valence structures, it is already important for molecules of intermediate size, like tetrabenzanthracene and

tribenzoperylene, both of which have five π -aromatic sextets. In both these cases the total number of conjugated circuits, given by $K(K-1)$, which is necessary to analyse, will be reduced by $2^5 = 32$. Thus in the case of tetrabenzanthracene ($K = 40$) instead of construction 39 conjugated circuits one needs to consider only 7 for Kekulé valence structures having five π -sextets, and in tribenzoperylene ($K = 45$) instead of 44 conjugated circuits one needs to consider only 12 for Kekulé valence structures having five π -sextets. For Kekulé valence structures having fewer π -sextets similar reductions are possible but as the number of π -sextets decrease one needs to construct additional conjugated circuits. In Fig. 9 we show the resulting π -electron patterns for tetrabenzanthracene and tribenzoperylene.

Discussion

Let us first consider the π -electron current pattern in cata-condensed triphenylene and tetrabenzanthracene.

Fig. 8. CC π -bond currents for two peri-condensed fully benzenoid hydrocarbons investigated.

From Fig. 7 we see that in the case of triphenylene the π -sextet rings are accompanied with dominant π -currents. The central ring of triphenylene, the “empty” ring in the terminology of Clar²⁷, is devoid on any ring current, because bond current directions in adjacent CC bonds alternate. One can decompose the π -electron current pattern in triphenylene into peripheral current of intensity 16 and ring currents in the three π -sextet rings of intensity 24, which when superimposed produce the current

pattern shown in Fig. 7. Alternatively one can interpret the bond currents as ring currents as shown in the lower part of Fig. 7.

In the current pattern for tetrabenzoanthracene shows similar characteristics : In this molecule the dominant current runs within the π -sextet rings while minor current accompanies molecular periphery. As one can see from Fig. 9 peripheral current intensity is 328, the ter-

Fig. 9. The nine Kekulé valence structures of triphenylene.

Fig. 10. Conjugated circuits in the first Kekulé valence structure of triphenylene of Fig. 9.

minal rings carry diamagnetic currents of amplitude 1000 and 1012. We should add that we use for measure unit 1 for contribution of a single conjugated circuit so that results are integers. However, if one is to compare CC bond currents in different molecules, which generally will have different number of Kekulé valence structures, the resulting amplitudes should be normalized, dividing them by $K(k-1)$, where K is the number of Kekulé valence structures is in a molecule. In Table 1 we show so normalized CC bond currents for the four fully aromatic benzenoids considered in this work.

The π -currents in the two peri-condensed compounds of Fig. 1 show some common regularity. In both compounds very pronounced are the ring currents in π -sextet rings. This has also been the case in triphenylene, but no so pronounced, which apparently is not typical cata-condensed benzenoid in this respect. When one partitions the π -electron ring current patterns into ring currents, the magnitude of ring currents on molecular periphery is determined by the smallest CC bond current in the ring, which are for dibenzopyrene 72 and 128 for the central top and bottom pyrene benzene rings, and terminal

Fig. 11. Top : Unique conjugated circuits of Kekulé valence structures *A-H* of triphenylene; Bottom : All conjugated circuits of the last Kekulé valence structure *I* of triphenylene.

Table 1. Normalized CC bond currents for the four compounds considered

	Current per conjugated circuit				
$C_{18}H_{12}$	$40/72 = 0.55555$	$24/72 = 0.33333$	$16/72 = 0.22222$		
$C_{30}H_{18}$	$800/1560 = 0.51202$	$792/1560 = 0.50769$	$512/1560 = 0.32308$	$504/1569 = 0.32308$	$288/1560 = 0.18462$
$C_{24}H_{14}$	$200/380 = 0.52632$	$198/380 = 0.52105$	$128/380 = 0.33684$	$126/380 = 0.33158$	$72/380 = 0.18947$
$C_{30}H_{16}$	$1012/1980 = 0.51111$	$1000/1980 = 0.50505$	$684/1980 = 0.34545$	$672/1980 = 0.33939$	$612/1980 = 0.30909$
	$600/1980 = 0.30303$	$400/1980 = 0.20202$	$328/1980 = 0.16566$	$72/1980 = 0.03636$	

tetracene fragment rings, respectively. In tribenzoperylene the smallest CC bond current are 600, 612 and again 600 for the top, middle and central π -sextet rings, respectively. From Fig. 8 it clearly follows that dominant current pattern in peri-condensed fully benzenoid compounds are π -sextet currents.

Observe that in cata-condensed and peri-condensed fully benzenoid compounds studied there are no ring currents in the “empty” benzene rings, in which at least one CC bond current is missing or runs in the opposite direction. To which extent these finding will be found in other fully benzenoid hydrocarbons, and to which degree they

will be found by *ab initio* calculations remain to be seen, but at least for now our results support the notion of π -electron sextets of Eric Clar.

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References

1. J. A. Pople, *Mol. Phys.*, 1958, **1**, 175.
2. R. McWeeny, *Mol. Phys.*, 1958, **1**, 311.
3. G. G. Hall and A. Hardisson, *Proc. Roy. Soc. A, Math. & Phys. Sci.*, 1962, **268**, 328.
4. K. Jug, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1982, **48**, 1344.
5. J. A. N. F. Gomez and R. B. Mallion, *Chem. Rev.*, 2001, **101**, 1349.
6. P. Von Rague Schleyer, C. Maerkar, A. Dransfeld, H. Jiao, J. R. Nicolaas and J. R. Eikema Hommes, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **118**, 637.
7. G. Merino, T. Heiner and G. Seifert, *Chem. Eur. J.*, 2004, **10**, 4367.
8. M. P. Johansson, J. Jusélius and D. Sundholm, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2001, **44**, 1843.
9. E. Steiner, P. W. Fowler and L. W. Jenneskens, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.*, 2001, **40**, 362.
10. E. Steiner and P. W. Fowler, *J. Phys. Chem. (A)*, 2001, **105**, 9553.
11. E. Steiner and P. W. Fowler, *Chem. Commun.*, 2001, 2220.
12. P. W. Fowler and E. Steiner, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 2002, **364**, 259.
13. A. Soncini, E. Steiner, P. W. Fowler, R. W. A. Havenith and L. W. Jenneskens, *Chem. Eur. J.*, 2003, 2974.
14. R. W. A. Havenith, A. J. H. M. Meijer, B. J. Irving and P. W. Fowler, *Mol. Phys.*, 2009, **10**.
15. A. T. Balaban, D. E. Bean and P. W. Fowler, *Acta Chim. Slovenica*, 2010, **57**, 507.
16. R. B. Mallion, *Croat. Chem. Acta*, 2008, **81**, 227.
17. M. Randić, M. Nović, M. Vračko, D. Vukičević and Dejan Plavšić, *Int. J. Quantum. Chem.* (submitted).
18. M. Randić, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 2010, **500**, 123.
19. Gaussian 09, Revision A.02, M. J. Frisch, G. W. Trucks, H. B. Schlegel, G. E. Scuseria, M. A. Robb, J. R. Cheeseman, G. Scalmani, V. Barone, B. Mennucci, G. A. Peterson, H. Nakatsuji, M. Caricato, X. Li, H. P. Hratchian, A. F. Izmaylov, J. Bloino, G. Zheng, J. L. Sonnenberg, M. Hada, M. Ehara, K. Toyota, R. Fukuda, J. Hasegawa, M. Ishida, T. Nakajima, Y. Honda, O. Kitao, H. Nakai, T. Vreven, J. A. Montgomery (Jr.), J. E. Peralta, F. Ogliarico, M. Bearpark, J. J. Heyd, E. Brothers, K. N. Kudion, V. N. Staroverov, R. Kobayashi, J. Normand, K. Raghavachari, A. Rendell, J. C. Burant, S. S. Iyengar, J. Tomasi, M. Cossi, N. Rega, J. M. Milloam, M. Klenc, J. E. Knox, J. B. Cross, V. Bakken, C. Adamo, J. Jaramillo, R. Gomperts, R. E. Stratmann, O. Yazyev, A. J. Austin, R. Cammi, C. Pomelli, J. W. Ochterski, L. R. Martin, K. Morokuma, V. G. Zakrzewski, G. A. Voth, P. Salvador, J. J. Dannenberg, S. Dapprich, A. D. Daniels, O. Farkas, J. B. Foresman, J. V. Ortiz, J. Cioslowski and D. J. Fox, Gaussian, Inc. Wallingford, CT, 2009.
20. M. Randić, *Chem. Rev.*, 2003, **103**, 3449.
21. M. Randić, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1976, **38**, 68.
22. M. Randić, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **99**, 444.
23. M. Randić, *Tetrahedron*, 1977, **33**, 1905.
24. S. Nikolić, M. Randić, D. J. Klein, D. Plavšić and N. Trinajstić, *J. Mol. Struct.*, 1989, **198**, 223.
25. I. Gutman and M. Randić, *Chem. Phys.*, 1979, **41**, 265.
26. M. Randić, D. Vukičević, M. Nović and D. Plavšić, (work in progress).
27. E. Clar, "The Aromatic Sextet", Wiley, London, 1972.

